

Continuity Equation Versus Free Particle Flow/Flux Quantum Equations III

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In Part II we noted that in the literature the Schrodinger equation is sometimes derived (e.g. (1)) from two fluid equations which follow from Boltzmann's transport equation, namely the continuity equation (conservation of mass) and a conservation of momentum equation. We also suggested the following flow/flux equations for a free particle: $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ ((1a)) and $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$ ((1b)) or $A = -Et + px$ a Lorentz invariant. For a quantum free particle one may convert these into eigenvalue equations (see Part II). For a bound state one has a system with no overall net momentum, but an overall energy. Thus one may expect the free particle quantum solution $\exp(-iEt)$ to still appear.

In (1), $u(x,t)$ = velocity field is defined as $d/dx S(x,t)$ based on the idea of irrotational flow. We argued that for $u(x,t)=0$ $S(x,t)=f(t)$ where t is any function which is ambiguous. Furthermore, in order to have the equations of (1) apply for a bound state $S=-Et$ or in other words there is a principle that $d/dt S = -E$ i.e ((1b)).

In this note we examine both a free quantum particle and a bound state in terms of the fluid approach of (1). The result $S=-Et$ remains, but in the case of the free particle ((1a)) emerges from $dS/dx = u(x,t)=p$. For the bound state overall p is 0, but $S=-Et$ still holds. As a result there is a density from the fluid approach and a related stress potential which leads to a conservation of energy equation. The stress potential, however, is equal to the average kinetic energy at each x because $E = W(x) + V(x)$ from (1). In (1) $W(x)$ is calculated using assumptions linking $s_{ij} = \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$ to derivatives of density. We calculate average kinetic energy directly using: $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / Wv(x)$ where $Wv(x)$ = wavefunction = $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The two results are the same.

Free Quantum Particle in the Fluid Approach of (1)

In (1) the Schrodinger equation is derived using two well-known classical fluid equations:

$d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t) + \text{grad dot } d(x,t) u(x,t) = 0$ where $d(x,t)$ =spatial density and $u(x,t)$ a velocity field ((2a)) and

$d/dt \text{ partial } (m d(x,t) u_i(x,t)) + d/dx_j (d(x,t) s_{ij}) + d(x,t)dV/dx = 0$ ((2b))

where $s_{ij} = \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$. We consider one dimension in this note. In (1) it is argued that $u(x,t)$ is irrotational and so should satisfy:

$u(x,t) = d/dx S(x,t)$ ((3))

For a free particle, $u(x,t) = p = \text{constant}$ thus giving the flux/flow equation $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ ((1a)) As noted in Part II there is ambiguity with $S(x,t)$ as:

$S(x,t) = f(t)$ for any function f gives $u=0$ ((4))

Furthermore, in (1) an energy conservation equation is obtained. This imposes a further restriction on $S(x,t)$ for a free particle. In fact it leads to the second flux/flow equation $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$ as is shown.

In (1) Newton's equation is used:

$$M \frac{d}{dt} \text{ full } u = F(\text{fluid stress}) + F(\text{from } V) \quad ((5)) \text{ with } F(\text{fluid}) = -dW/dx \text{ and } F(V) = -dV/dx$$

Here W is a fluid type potential.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{ full} = \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} + u \frac{d}{dx} \quad ((6)) \text{ Using } u = 1/m \frac{d}{dx} S \text{ one has from } ((5))$$

$$M \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dS}{dt} \text{ partial} + .5 \left(\frac{d}{dx} \text{ partial } S \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \text{ partial } S \right) \right) = -\frac{d}{dx} \{ W+V \} \quad ((6))$$

Pulling out d/dx yields the usual conservation of energy equation for a free particle with $W=0$ and $V=0$. This means, however, that $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$, in other words S for a free particle A in ((1b)). In pulling d/dx out of ((6)) one could introduce another constant, but $dS/dt \text{ partial}$ is already present and is part of the conservation equation. Furthermore dS/dt is maintained throughout (1) in the derivation of the Schrodinger equation. In other words $dS/dt \text{ partial}$ represents the constant namely $-E$.

Thus a fluid treatment with the assumption $u(x,t) = dS(x,t)/dx$ leads to the two flux/flow equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) which solve the quantum free particle problem when written as eigenvalue equations.

Bound State Case

The bound quantum solution differs. We still maintain $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ as there is an overall energy for the bound system (actually masses plus binding energy E), but no overall momentum. Thus $\exp(-iEt+px)$ is still a solution (multiplied by $\exp(-i(\text{mass sum})t)$ for the bound state seen as an "overall" free particle, but one does not know E .

The conservation equation ((6)) from (1) still applies with the d/dx operator removed. $V(x)$ is the usual potential and $W(x)$ a fluid stress potential which is expressed in (1) in terms of derivatives of density. Thus by examining the equations in (1) for a bound quantum state one has $S = -Et$ and spatial density $d(x,t)$, but $u(x,t) = dS/dx = 0$. As a result the bound quantum system is treated in a classical manner with some assumptions applied to the calculation of $W(x)$ the fluid stress. One may, however, make immediate assumptions about $W(x)$ from the conservation equation ((6)) applied to a bound state with $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ and $dS/dx = 0 = u$.

$$-E = -W(x) - V(x) \quad ((7))$$

Thus: $W(x) =$ average kinetic energy at x within the fluid for a bound state.

As a result, there should be two approaches to calculating $W(x)$.

Approach A: Average Kinetic Energy from Fluid Stress Potential (approach of (1))

First is the approach of (1) i.e. trying to calculate a stress potential in a fluid. In (1) it is assumed that:

$$S_{ij} \text{ (from ((2b))) } = d/dx_i d/dx_j a(\ln(d(x,t))) \quad \text{where } a \text{ is an unknown function ((8))}$$

It is further argued that : $a(\ln(d)) = c_1 \ln(d) + c_2$ (c_1, c_2 being constants) ((9))

The final result of (1) is:

$$W = -bb/4m \{ .5 [d/dx \ln(d)] [d/dx \ln(d)] + d/dx d/dx \ln(d) \} \quad ((10)) \quad b = \text{constant}$$

Defining a bound state $d(x,t) = W_v(x)W_v(x)$ where $W_v(x)$ is like a wavefunction one finds that for an appropriate b (constant) one has the quantum mechanical expression for kinetic energy $(-1/2m d/dx dW_v/dx)/W_v$.

Approach B: Average Kinetic Energy from Probabilities

Given that $W(x)$ is equivalent to average kinetic energy as is shown by its role in the bound state conservation of energy equation $-E = -W - V$, it should be possible to calculate this average directly using probabilities. This recalls the free particle solution for which $d(x,t) = \text{constant}$ and $S = -Et + px$.

To see this more clearly from the flux/flow equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) consider:

$$id/dt \text{ partial exp}(iA) = E \text{ exp}(iA) \text{ and } -id/dx \text{ partial exp}(iA) = p \text{ exp}(iA)$$

In Part II we argued that $\text{exp}(iA)$ represents a kind of complex conditional probability $P(p/x)$.

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \text{ exp}(ipx) / W_v(x) \quad ((8)) \quad \text{i.e. } W_v(x) \text{ the wavefunction is a normalization function.}$$

Imagine for the time being that $W_v(x)$ is only a normalization factor in ((8)) with no connection to spatial density.

{ASIDE: It is possible to use the relationship $P(p/x) = P(p \text{ and } x) / P(x)$ and $P(x/p) = P(p \text{ and } x) / P(p)$ with some assumptions to show that $W_v(x)W_v(x) = P(x) = d(x)$ }

One may calculate the average kinetic energy using the unusual complex periodic $P(p/x)$ probability i.e.

$$KE \text{ ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) p^2/2m \text{ exp}(ipx)] / W_v(x) = \{-1/2m d/dx dW_v/dx\} / W_v \quad \text{where} \\ W_v(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \text{ exp}(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

This should be equivalent to $W(x)$. In the fluid approach, $W(x)$ was described in terms of derivatives of $\ln(d)$ so one may compare the two expressions and see that $W_v(x)W_v(x) = d(x,t)$ for a bound system (in which $W_v(x)$ is a real function).

Thus for a bound quantum state the fluid approach using the assumptions needed to calculate $s_{ij} = \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$ are equivalent to considering a free particle conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / \{W_v\}$ where $W_v = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and calculating average kinetic energy using the usual statistical definition except for the fact that the probability $P(p/x)$ is unusual.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for a free particle $S(x,t)$ defined by $u(x,t) = \text{velocity field} = d/dx S(x,t)$ for irrotational flow is $-Et + px$. In fact, $S=A$ from ((1a)) and ((1b)) in this case and leads to $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$. Furthermore one must impose $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$ in order for the fluid equations of (1) to yield the correct conservation of energy equation.

For a bound quantum state matters are different. $S = -Et$ because the overall p is 0. In (1) Newton's equation $m \, d/dt \text{ full } u = m \, d/dt \text{ partial } u + m \, u \cdot d/dx \text{ partial } u = F(\text{fluid stress}) + F$ usual is applied. $F_{\text{usual}} = -dV/dx$ and $F(\text{fluid stress}) = -dW/dx$ where $W(x)$ is unknown. A conservation of energy equation follows for which $W(x)$ must be average kinetic energy at x for a bound quantum state in which $u(x,t) = 0$. In such a case there are two ways to calculate W . In (1) the author makes assumptions about $s_{ij} = \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$ to express it in terms of derivatives of spatial density. We argue that average kinetic energy should also be expressible in terms of a probability linked to a free particle solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. We use $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(-ipx) / W_v(x)$ where $W_v(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that:

$$\text{KE ave } (x) = \{ \sum_p a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / W_v = \{ -1/2m \, d/dx \, dW_v/dx \} / W_v$$

The two approaches yield the same result. Thus for a quantum bound state the average kinetic energy at each x is like a fluid stress potential, but is also the mathematical average of $p^2/2m$ using $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W_v(x)$. It may be pointed out that a quantum bound state consists of only one bound particle so the physical picture of $d(x,t)$ differs from that of a system with many particles. Thus using the complex $\exp(ipx)$ is more than a mathematical approach we argue.

References

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